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Research Article

On γ - β -I Open and Closed Sets in Ideal Topological Spaces

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to extend the concept of γ - β -open sets to the framework of ideal topological spaces and to investigate the fundamental properties that arise from this generalization. Motivated by earlier studies on generalized open sets, such as γ -open, β -open, γ -semi-open, and I-open sets, we introduce and analyze γ - β -I open and γ - β -I closed sets within an ideal topological space (X, τ, I) . Several characterizations, inclusion relations, and closure and interior type operators associated with these new classes of sets are obtained.

Keywords: Ideal topological space, γ - β open sets, γ - β -I open sets

1. Introduction

The study of generalized open sets has long been an important part of modern topology. One of the earliest examples of such generalizations is the concept of semi-open sets introduced by Levine (1963). Since that time, many new types of generalized openness have been developed, each offering different ways to investigate topological structures. For example, Abd El-Monsef et al. (1983) introduced β -open sets, and later Tong (2006) expanded this idea by defining generalized β -open sets. These and similar concepts have been used to revisit various topological properties (Tahiliani, 2011; Kannan et al., 2012; Akdağ et al., 2014), leading to more refined results. In recent years, new classes of sets have also been applied to study deeper structural notions such as homotopy (Erciyes et al., 2016) and covering properties (Başar and Akız, 2025).

Another important development was introduced by Kasahara (1979), who defined an operation $\gamma: \tau \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(X)$ that assigns to each open set V a superset $\gamma(V)$. A set V is called γ -open if, for every point in V , there exists an open neighborhood U such that $\gamma(U) \subseteq V$. This idea led to further studies on γ -interior (Janković, 1983), γ -closure (Ogata, 1991), γ -semi-open sets (Ahmad et al., 2005; Hussain et al., 2010), γ -s-closed sets (Hussain et al., 2007), γ -pre-open sets (Krishnan et al., 2006), γ -b-open sets (Hussain, 2018), and γ - β -open sets (Basu et al., 2009). Together, these concepts form a broad framework that allows the topological structure of spaces to be studied in a more flexible manner.

Parallel to these developments, the theory of ideals led to the introduction of ideal topological spaces (X, τ, I) , where I is an ideal on X . In this context, Vaidyanathaswamy (1945) introduced the local function

$$A * (I, \tau) = \{x \in X : U \cap A \notin I \text{ for every neighborhood } U \text{ of } x\}$$

which was later used to define a Kuratowski-type closure operator $cl^*(A) = A \cup A^*(I, \tau)$ (Hayashi, 1964; Kuratowski, 1966). Janković (1992) then introduced the concept of I -open sets, establishing a strong connection between ideal theory and generalized openness.

New types of sets in ideal topological spaces have been studied by (Akız and Özcan, 2025) through the use of the gamma operator. Although γ - β -open sets have been investigated in classical topological spaces (Basu et al., 2009), their extension to ideal topological spaces has not yet been examined in detail. In this study, we extend the notion of γ - β -open sets to ideal topological spaces. By incorporating an ideal I into the structure of (X, τ) , we define γ - β - I open and γ - β - I closed

sets and investigate their main properties. Using these sets, we revisit γ -interior and γ -closure operators and examine how they interact with the ideal. We also compare γ - β - I sets with other generalized open sets, such as γ -open, β -open, and I -open sets, showing how the ideal contributes to a richer structure.

In the final part of the paper, we present several results describing how γ - β - I sets behave under unions, intersections, and complements. These observations indicate that γ - β - I sets provide a natural and meaningful extension of earlier generalized openness concepts. The framework introduced here can also support future studies on continuity, separation axioms, and operator-based topological constructions in ideal topological spaces.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 Let X be a nonempty set and let $P(X)$ denote the power set of X . A nonempty family $I \subseteq P(X)$ is called an ideal on X if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (a) If $M \in I$ and $N \subseteq M$, then $N \in I$.
- (b) If $M, N \in I$, then $M \cup N \in I$.

Such a family I is called an ideal on the set X (Kuratowski, 1933; Kuratowski, 1966).

From now on, let X be a topological space.

Definition 2.2. A subset $S \subseteq X$ is called a β -open set (Abd El-Monsef et al., 1983) if $S \subseteq \text{cl}(\text{int}(\text{cl}(S)))$.

Definition 2.3. Let I be an ideal on X . The triple (X, τ, I) is called an ideal topological space (Janković and Hamlett, 1993).

Definition 2.4. Let $S \subseteq X$, and let I be an ideal on X . The set $S^*(I, \tau) = \{x \in X \mid \forall R \in \mathcal{G}(x), (R \cap S) \notin I\}$

is called the local function of the set S with respect to the ideal I and the topology τ (Janković and Hamlett, 1990).

In this paper, we simply write S^* instead of $S^*(I, \tau)$.

Proposition 2.5. Let I be an ideal on X . For subsets $S, R \subseteq X$, the following properties hold (Kuratowski, 1933):

1. If $S \subseteq R$, then $S^* \subseteq R^*$.
2. $(S^*)^* \subseteq S^*$.
3. $(S \cup R)^* = S^* \cup R^*$.
4. $(S \cap R)^* \subseteq S^* \cap R^*$.
5. $S^* = \text{cl}(S^*) \subseteq \text{cl}(S)$.

Definition 2.6 Let I be an ideal on X . For a subset $S \subseteq X$, the operator

$$\text{cl}^*(S) = S \cup S^*$$

defines a mapping $\text{cl}^*: P(X) \rightarrow P(X)$ satisfying:

1. $\text{cl}^*(\emptyset) = \emptyset$,
2. $S \subseteq \text{cl}^*(S)$ for every $S \subseteq X$,
3. $\text{cl}^*(S \cup R) = \text{cl}^*(S) \cup \text{cl}^*(R)$ for all $S, R \subseteq X$,
4. $\text{cl}^*(\text{cl}^*(S)) = \text{cl}^*(S)$ for all $S \subseteq X$.

The operator cl^* is called the **Kuratowski -closure operator* (Kuratowski, 1933). The **-closure* of a set S will be denoted by $\text{cl}^*(S)$.

Definition 2.7. Let I be an ideal on X . A subset $S \subseteq X$ is called an I -open set if $S \subseteq \text{int}(S^*)$ (Abd El-Monsef, 1992).

Definition 2.8 A mapping

$$\gamma: \tau \rightarrow P(X)$$

is called a γ -operation if for every $S \in \tau$, $S \subseteq S_\gamma$, where S_γ denotes the value of S under the γ -operation (Kasahara, 1979). The family of all such operations on X is denoted by $\Gamma(X)$.

Definition 2.9. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. A point $x \in X$ is called a γ -closure point of S if for every open neighborhood R of x ,

$$R_\gamma \cap S \neq \emptyset.$$

The set of all γ -closure points of S is called the γ -closure of S and is denoted by

$$\text{cl}_\gamma(S).$$

If $\text{cl}_\gamma(S) \subseteq S$, then the subset S is called γ -closed. In this case, $\text{cl}_\gamma(S)$ contains every γ -closed subset of S (Ogata, 1991).

Definition 2.10. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. A point $x \in S$ is called a γ -interior point of S if there exists an open neighborhood R of x such that

$$R_\gamma \subseteq S.$$

The set of all γ -interior points of S is called the γ -interior of S and is denoted by $\text{int}_\gamma(S)$. Explicitly,

$$\text{int}_\gamma(S) = \{x \in S \mid \exists R \in \tau \text{ such that } x \in R \text{ and } R_\gamma \subseteq S\}.$$

Thus,

$$\text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq S.$$

Moreover:

(i) S is γ -open if and only if $\text{int}_\gamma(S) = S$.

(ii) If $S \subseteq P$, then

$$\text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(P) \text{ and } \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(P)$$

(Rehman and Ahmad, 1992).

Definition 2.11. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$. For a subset $S \subseteq X$, if $S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(S)))$, then S is called a γ - β -open set. If the complement S^c is γ - β -open, then S is called a γ - β -closed set. Moreover, if S is γ - β -closed, then $\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(S))) \subseteq S$ (Basu et al., 2009).

Theorem 2.12. (Akız and Özcan, 2025) Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space, $\gamma \in \Omega(X)$, and $A, B \subseteq X$. Then:

1. **(i)** If $A \subseteq B$, then $A_\gamma^* \subseteq B_\gamma^*$.
2. **(ii)** $(A_\gamma^*)_\gamma^* = A_\gamma^*$.
3. **(iii)** $(A \cup B)_\gamma^* = A_\gamma^* \cup B_\gamma^*$.
4. **(iv)** $(A \cap B)_\gamma^* = A_\gamma^* \cap B_\gamma^*$.

Theorem 3.13. (Akız and Özcan, 2025) Let (X, τ, I) be an ideal topological space, $\gamma \in \Omega(X)$, and $A, B \subseteq X$.

The Kuratowski closure operator $\text{cl}_\gamma^*(\cdot)$ satisfies the following conditions:

1. **(i)** $\text{cl}_\gamma^*(\emptyset) = \emptyset$.
2. **(ii)** $A \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma^*(A)$.
3. **(iii)** $\text{cl}_\gamma^*(A \cup B) = \text{cl}_\gamma^*(A) \cup \text{cl}_\gamma^*(B)$.
4. **(iv)** $\text{cl}_\gamma^*(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(A)) = \text{cl}_\gamma^*(A)$.

3. γ - β -I Sets and Their Properties

From this point onward, X will be regarded as an ideal topological space equipped with the structure (X, τ, I) .

Definition 3.1. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. If $S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S)))$, then S is called a γ - β -I open set. The family of all γ - β -I open sets will be denoted by $\beta IO_\gamma(X)$.

Definition 3.2 Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. If $S \supseteq \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma^*(S)))$, then S is called a γ - β -I closed set. The family of all γ - β -I closed sets will be denoted by $\beta IC_\gamma(X)$.

Proposition 3.3. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. If S is γ - β -I open, then its complement S^c is γ - β -I closed.

Proof. Assume that S is γ - β -I open. Then

$$S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))).$$

Taking complements, we obtain

$$S^c \supseteq (\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))))^c = \text{int}_\gamma((\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S)))^c) = \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma((\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))^c)).$$

Since $(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))^c = \text{int}_\gamma^*(S^c)$, we obtain

$$S^c \supseteq \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma^*(S^c))).$$

Thus S^c is γ - β -I closed.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{t, p, l\}$ with the topology $\tau = \{\emptyset, X, \{t\}, \{r\}, \{t, p\}\}$, and let $I = \{\emptyset, \{t\}\}$. Define an operation $\gamma: \tau \rightarrow P(X)$ by

$$\gamma(S) = S_\gamma = \begin{cases} S, & p \in S, \\ \text{cl}(S), & p \notin S. \end{cases}$$

Then, γ -open sets are $\emptyset, X, \{t, l\}, \{p\}, \{t, p\}$.

γ -closed sets are $\emptyset, X, \{t, l\}, \{p\}, \{l\}$.

γ - β -I open sets are $\emptyset, X, \{t, l\}, \{p\}, \{t, p\}, \{p, l\}$.

γ - β -I closed sets are $\emptyset, X, \{t, l\}, \{p\}, \{l\}, \{t\}$.

For $S = \{p, l\}$, we have $\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))) = X$, and since $S \subseteq X$, the set S is γ - β -I open.

For $R = \{t\}$, $\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(R))) = \emptyset$, and $R \not\subseteq \emptyset$. Therefore R is not γ - β -I open.

Theorem 3.5. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$. The following statements hold,

- (i) An arbitrary union of γ - β -I open sets is γ - β -I open.
- (ii) An arbitrary intersection of γ - β -I closed sets is γ - β -I closed.

Proof.

(i) Let $\{S_i: i \in J\} \subseteq \beta IO_\gamma(X)$. For each i , $S_i \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S_i)))$.

Hence

$$\bigcup_{i \in J} S_i \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in J} \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S_i))) = \text{cl}_\gamma\left(\bigcup_{i \in J} \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S_i))\right) \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\bigcup_{i \in J} \text{cl}_\gamma^*(S_i))).$$

Thus

$$\bigcup_{i \in J} S_i \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(\bigcup_{i \in J} S_i))),$$

so the union is γ - β -I open.

(ii) Let $\{S_i: i \in J\} \subseteq \beta IC_\gamma(X)$. For each i , $S_i \supseteq \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma^*(S_i)))$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_{i \in J} S_i &\supseteq \bigcap_{i \in J} \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma^*(S_i))) = \text{int}_\gamma\left(\bigcap_{i \in J} \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma^*(S_i))\right) \supseteq \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma\left(\bigcap_{i \in J} \text{int}_\gamma^*(S_i)\right)) \\ &= \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma^*\left(\bigcap_{i \in J} S_i\right))). \end{aligned}$$

Thus the intersection is γ - β -I closed.

Theorem 3.6. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. Then the following statements hold:

- i. If S is γ -open, then S is γ - β -I open.
- ii. If S is γ -I-open, then S is γ - β -I open.
- iii. If S is γ -pre-I-open, then S is γ - β -I open.
- iv. Every γ - β -I open set is γ - β open.

Proof (i) Assume that S is γ -open. Then $S \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S)$. Since $S \subseteq S^* \cup S$, by (Rehman, 1992), $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow \text{int}_\gamma(A) \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(B)$. Then, we obtain:

$$\text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S).$$

Combining the two inclusions gives

$$S \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S).$$

Next, since $A \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(A)$, we have

$$\text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S) \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S)).$$

Finally, observe that:

$$S^* \cup S = \text{cl}_\gamma^*(S),$$

so we may rewrite the final term as

$$\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))).$$

Thus,

$$S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))),$$

which is precisely the definition of γ - β -I-openness.

(ii) Assume that S is γ -I-open. Then

$$S \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S^*).$$

Since $S^* \subseteq S^* \cup S$, we have

$$\text{int}_\gamma(S^*) \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S).$$

Thus:

$$S \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S).$$

Hence,

$$S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S)) = \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))),$$

which proves that S is γ - β -I-open.

(iii) Assume that S is γ -I-open. Then we have $S \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S^*)$. Since $S^* \subseteq S^* \cup S$ then we get $\text{int}_\gamma(S^*) \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S)$.

Thus, $S \subseteq \text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S)$. Hence,

$$S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S)) = \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))),$$

which proves that S is γ - β -I-open.

(iv) Assume that S is γ - β -I open. Then $S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S)))$. Note that $\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S) \subseteq S^* \cup S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \cup S$. Thus, $S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(S))) \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(S^* \cup S)) \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(S) \cup S)) \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(S)))$. Therefore, $S \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(S)))$, which means S is γ - β open.

The converse, however, is not true. For instance (Example 3.4), the set $S = \{a\}$ satisfies $\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(S))) = \{a, c\}$, and since $\{a\} \subseteq \{a, c\}$, the set $\{a\}$ is γ - β open. But it is not γ - β -I open.

Definition 3.7. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$.

The γ - β -I closure of S is defined as the intersection of all γ - β -I closed sets containing S , and is denoted by

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) = \bigcap \{ R \mid S \subseteq R \text{ and } R^c \in \beta IO_\gamma(X) \}.$$

The γ - β -I interior of S is the union of all γ - β -I open sets contained in S , and is denoted by

$$\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) = \bigcup \{ P \mid P \subseteq S, P \in \beta IO_\gamma(X) \}.$$

Theorem 3.8. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. Then the following assertions hold:

1. $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(\emptyset) = \emptyset$ and $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(\emptyset) = \emptyset$.
2. $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$ is γ - β -I closed in X .
3. $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$ is γ - β -I open in X .
4. $S \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$.
5. $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq S$.
6. S is γ - β -I open if and only if $S = \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$.
7. S is γ - β -I closed if and only if $S = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$.
8. If $S \subseteq P$, then $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(P)$.
9. If $S \subseteq P$, then $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(P)$.
10. $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)) = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$.
11. $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)) = \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$.
12. $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \cup \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cup R)$.
13. $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cap R) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \cap \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R)$.

Proof (1) We first verify the behavior of the γ - β -I closure and interior on the empty set, using the basic definitions. Since

$$\emptyset \subseteq \text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma^*(\emptyset))) \text{ and } \emptyset \supseteq \text{int}_\gamma(\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma^*(\emptyset))),$$

it follows from the definitions that both the γ - β -I closure and γ - β -I interior of \emptyset coincide with \emptyset .

(2) We now show that the γ - β -I closure of a set is always γ - β -I closed by directly applying the definition as an intersection of all such closed supersets. By Definition 3.7,

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) = \bigcap \{ R \mid S \subseteq R \text{ and } R^c \in \beta IO_\gamma(X) \}.$$

This is the intersection of γ - β -I closed sets, hence $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$ is γ - β -I closed.

(3) Similarly, by Definition 3.7,

$$\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) = \cup\{P \mid P \subseteq S, P \in \beta IO_\gamma(X)\},$$

which is a union of γ - β -I open sets; therefore $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$ is γ - β -I open.

(4) We show that every set is contained in its γ - β -I closure by construction of the closure operator. The set $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$ is defined as the intersection of all γ - β -I closed sets containing S . Hence it is the smallest γ - β -I closed set containing S , and thus necessarily $S \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$.

(5) Similarly, the γ - β -I interior is always contained in the set itself by Definition 3.7. The set $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$ is defined as the union of all γ - β -I open subsets of S . Therefore it is the largest γ - β -I open set contained in S , and we have $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq S$.

(6) We now characterize γ - β -I open sets in terms of the γ - β -I interior operator. Suppose first that S is γ - β -I open. Then $S \in \beta IO_\gamma(X)$ and, since $S \subseteq S$, we have S among the sets used in the definition of $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$. Thus

$$S \subseteq \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S).$$

On the other hand, by (5), $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq S$. Hence

$$S = \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S).$$

Conversely, if $S = \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$, then S is the γ - β -I interior of a set, and by (3) it must be γ - β -I open.

(7) Suppose first that S is γ - β -I closed. Then $S^c \in \beta IO_\gamma(X)$ and $S \subseteq S$, so S occurs in the family whose intersection defines $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$. Thus

$$S \supseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$$

is clear from the definition, while (4) gives $S \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$. Hence

$$S = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S).$$

Conversely, if $S = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$, then S is a γ - β -I closure of a set and thus γ - β -I closed.

(8) We have

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) = \cap\{R \mid S \subseteq R, R^c \in \beta IO_\gamma(X)\} \text{ and } \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(P) = \cap\{R \mid P \subseteq R, R^c \in \beta IO_\gamma(X)\}.$$

If $S \subseteq P$, then every γ - β -I closed set R containing P also contains S . Thus

$$\bigcap_{R_S \supseteq S} R_S \subseteq \bigcap_{R_P \supseteq P} R_P,$$

and consequently $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(P)$.

(9) Similarly,

$$\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) = \cup\{R \mid R \subseteq S, R \in \beta IO_\gamma(X)\}, \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(P) = \cup\{R \mid R \subseteq P, R \in \beta IO_\gamma(X)\}.$$

If $S \subseteq P$, then every γ - β -I open set R with $R \subseteq S$ is also a subset of P . Hence

$$\bigcup_{R_S \subseteq S} R_S \subseteq \bigcup_{R_P \subseteq P} R_P,$$

and therefore $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(P)$.

(10) Since $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$ is γ - β -I closed by (2), applying the γ - β -I closure once more yields

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)) = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S).$$

(11) Since $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$ is γ - β -I open by (3), we have

$$\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)) = \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S).$$

(12) Since $S \subseteq S \cup R$ and $R \subseteq S \cup R$, it follows from (8) that $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cup R)$ and $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cup R)$.

Hence

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \cup \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cup R).$$

On the other hand, this inclusion may be proper. Consider again the space $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$, $I = \{\emptyset, \{a\}\}$,

with $\gamma: \tau \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(X)$ defined by

$$\gamma(S) = \begin{cases} S, & b \in S, \\ \text{cl}(S), & b \notin S. \end{cases}$$

Then γ -open, γ -closed, γ - β -I open and γ - β -I closed sets are as in Example 3.4. In this setting, for $S = \{b\}$ and $R = \{a\}$, we have

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) = \{b\}, \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R) = \{a\},$$

while

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cup R) = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(\{a, b\}) = X.$$

Thus

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \cup \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R) = \{a, b\} \subsetneq X = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cup R).$$

(13) Since $S \cap R \subseteq S$ and $S \cap R \subseteq R$, it follows from (8) that $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cap R) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$ and $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cap R) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R)$.

Hence

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cap R) \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \cap \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R).$$

Again, this inclusion may be proper. In the same example as above, take $S = \{a, c\}$ and $R = \{b, c\}$. Then

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) = \{a, c\}, \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R) = X,$$

while

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cap R) = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(\{c\}) = \{c\}.$$

Thus

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S \cap R) = \{c\} \subsetneq \{a, c\} = \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \cap \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(R).$$

Theorem 3.9. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. Then,

- i. $\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c) = (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c$.
- ii. $(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S))^c = \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c)$.

Proof:

(i) Since $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S) \subseteq S$, we have

$$S^c \subseteq (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c.$$

Moreover, $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S)$ is γ - β -I open, so its complement $(\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c$ is γ - β -I closed. Hence

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma((\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c) = (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c.$$

From $S^c \subseteq (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c$ we deduce

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c) \subseteq (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c.$$

On the other hand, by (4.1.8)(4), $S^c \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c)$, hence

$$(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c))^c \subseteq S.$$

The set $(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c))^c$ is γ - β -I open, so

$$\beta I \text{int}_\gamma((\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c))^c) = (\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c))^c.$$

Since $(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c))^c \subseteq S$, we obtain

$$(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c))^c \subseteq \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S),$$

and by taking complements again,

$$(\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c).$$

Combining both inclusions yields

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S^c) = (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S))^c.$$

(ii) Since $S \subseteq \beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S)$, we have

$$(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S))^c \subseteq S^c.$$

Thus

$$\beta I \text{int}_\gamma((\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S))^c) \subseteq \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c).$$

But $(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S))^c$ is γ - β -I open (as the complement of a γ - β -I closed set), hence

$$\beta I \text{int}_\gamma((\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S))^c) = (\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S))^c,$$

and we obtain

$$(\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S))^c \subseteq \beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c).$$

Conversely, $\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c) \subseteq S^c$, hence

$$S \subseteq (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c))^c.$$

The set $(\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c))^c$ is γ - β -I closed, and thus

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma((\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c))^c) = (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c))^c.$$

From $S \subseteq (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c))^c$ we deduce

$$\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S) \subseteq (\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c))^c,$$

and taking complements,

$$\beta I \text{int}_\gamma(S^c) \subseteq (\beta I \text{cl}_\gamma(S))^c.$$

Therefore,

$$(\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S))^c = \beta Iint_{\gamma}(S^c).$$

Theorem 3.10. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$, and let $S \subseteq X$. Then:

- (i) $\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S) = S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S)))$.
- (ii) $\beta Iint_{\gamma}(S) = S \cap cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}^*(S)))$.

Proof: (i) Since $\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S)$ is γ - β -I closed by Theorem 3.8 (ii), it must contain $int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S))))$.

This is because for any set A, the expression

$$int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(A)))$$

is always a γ - β -I open set containing A. Every γ - β -I closed set must contain all γ - β -I open sets that lie inside it.

Hence,

$$S \cup \beta Icl_{\gamma}(S) \supseteq S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S)))).$$

So we have

$$\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S) \supseteq S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S)))).$$

Using the definition of int_{γ}^* , we get

$$\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S) \supseteq S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S))).$$

To prove the reverse inclusion, we show that the set

$$S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S)))$$

is γ - β -I closed.

By applying the operators, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S)))))) &\subseteq int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S) \cup int_{\gamma}^*(int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S)))))) \\ &\subseteq int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S) \cup cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S)))) \\ &\subseteq int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S)))) \\ &= int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S))) \\ &\subseteq S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S))). \end{aligned}$$

These steps follow from basic properties of interior and closure of int_{γ}^* .

Thus the set is γ - β -I closed.

So,

$$\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S)))) = S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S))).$$

Since $\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S)$ is the smallest γ - β -I closed set containing S, we get

$$\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S) \subseteq S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S))).$$

Together with the earlier inclusion, we obtain

$$\beta Icl_{\gamma}(S) = S \cup int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}^*(S))).$$

(ii) Since $\beta Iint_{\gamma}(S)$ is γ - β -I open by Theorem 3.8 (iii), we have

$$\beta Iint_{\gamma}(S) \subseteq cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}^*(\beta Iint_{\gamma}(S)))).$$

Using $\beta Iint_{\gamma}(S) \subseteq S$, we get

$$\beta Iint_{\gamma}(S) \subseteq S \cap cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}^*(\beta Iint_{\gamma}(S)))) \subseteq S \cap cl_{\gamma}(int_{\gamma}(cl_{\gamma}^*(S))).$$

To get the reverse inclusion, we show that

$$S \cap cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S)))$$

is γ - β - I open. This is necessary because $\beta Int_\gamma(S)$ is defined as the largest γ - β - I open set contained in S .

We compute:

$$\begin{aligned} cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S \cap cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S))))) &\supseteq cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S) \cap cl_\gamma^*(cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S))))) \\ &\supseteq cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S) \cap int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S)))) \\ &= cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S))) \\ &\supseteq S \cap cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S))). \end{aligned}$$

Thus the set is γ - β - I open, and

$$\beta Int_\gamma(S \cap cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S)))) = S \cap cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S))).$$

Since $\beta Int_\gamma(S)$ is the largest γ - β - I open subset of S , we get

$$\beta Int_\gamma(S) \supseteq S \cap cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S))).$$

Together with the first inclusion, we conclude

$$\beta Int_\gamma(S) = S \cap cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S))).$$

Example 3.11. Let $X = \mathbb{N}$ with the discrete topology $\tau = \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$. Let the ideal $I = \text{Fin}$ be the family of all finite subsets of \mathbb{N} :

$$\text{Fin} = \{F \subseteq \mathbb{N} : F \text{ is finite}\}.$$

Define $\gamma: \tau \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(X)$ by

$$\gamma(U) = \begin{cases} \emptyset, & U = \emptyset, \\ U \cup \{1\}, & U \text{ finite and nonempty,} \\ U, & U \text{ infinite.} \end{cases}$$

This γ satisfies $U \subseteq \gamma(U)$ for every open U , so $\gamma \in \Gamma(X)$.

Since the topology is discrete, every singleton $\{x\}$ is open.

The local function

$$S^* = \{x \in X : \text{for every open } U \ni x, U \cap S \notin \text{Fin}\}$$

is always empty, because for any x we have $\{x\} \cap S \in \text{Fin}$. Thus, for every $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$,

$$S^* = \emptyset, cl_\gamma^*(S) = S \cup S^* = S.$$

To compute γ -closure, we use the singleton neighborhood of each point:

$$\gamma(\{x\}) = \begin{cases} \{1\}, & x = 1, \\ \{x, 1\}, & x \neq 1. \end{cases}$$

Hence, if $1 \in S$ then every $\gamma(\{x\})$ meets S , and therefore $cl_\gamma(S) = \mathbb{N}$.

If $1 \notin S$, then only those $x \in S$ satisfy $\gamma(\{x\}) \cap S \neq \emptyset$. Thus, $cl_\gamma(S) = S$ when $1 \notin S$.

Similarly, the γ -interior of a set $T \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ is determined by whether $\gamma(\{x\}) \subseteq T$. If $1 \in T$, then for every $x \in T$ we have $\gamma(\{x\}) \subseteq T$; hence $int_\gamma(T) = T$.

If $1 \notin T$, then no singleton neighborhood of any point satisfies $\gamma(\{x\}) \subseteq T$, so $int_\gamma(T) = \emptyset$.

Now, using Definition 3.1, we compute $cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S))) = cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(S))$.

If $1 \in S$, then $int_\gamma(S) = S$, and so $cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(S)) = cl_\gamma(S) = \mathbb{N}$.

Thus the inclusion $S \subseteq cl_\gamma(int_\gamma(cl_\gamma^*(S)))$ always holds whenever $1 \in S$. Therefore every set that contains the point 1 is γ - β - I open.

If $1 \notin S$, then $\text{int}_\gamma(S) = \emptyset$, and so $\text{cl}_\gamma(\text{int}_\gamma(S)) = \text{cl}_\gamma(\emptyset) = \emptyset$.

Hence $S \subseteq \emptyset$ only when $S = \emptyset$. Thus, in this example the family of γ - β -I open sets is exactly

$$\beta IO_\gamma(X) = \{\emptyset\} \cup \{S \subseteq \mathbb{N} : 1 \in S\}.$$

Consequently, the γ - β -I closed sets are precisely all subsets of \mathbb{N} that do not contain the point 1, together with the whole space \mathbb{N} .

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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4. Conclusion

In recent years, various notions of open sets in general topology have been widely studied. By using these new types of open sets, the notions of interior and closure have been redefined, showing that some concepts in topology may exhibit both different and similar properties. Together with the idea of an ideal, it becomes possible to move from classical topological spaces to ideal topological spaces and to examine these new set definitions in this extended framework.

In this study, generalized open sets defined through the γ -operation in classical topological spaces are adapted to the setting of ideal topological spaces. The new class obtained in this context, called γ - β -I open sets, provides a broader structure that allows the reinterpretation of several fundamental topological concepts. By using γ - β -I open sets, the notions of interior and closure are redefined, and their main properties are examined in detail. The results of this work show that many other concepts originally defined in topological spaces can also be extended to ideal topological spaces by means of the γ -operation. Therefore, the framework developed here lays a foundation for further

generalizations and opens new directions for research in the theory of ideal topological structures.

Future studies will focus on the concept of continuity, especially on how different types of continuity behave within the framework of γ - β -I open sets. In addition, this study presents a method for generating new sets. It is expected that this will contribute to increasing the variety of sets, thereby shedding light on the investigation of new properties in both topological and ideal topological spaces.

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